

STATUS OF INTESTINAL PARASITIC INFECTIONS AMONG PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THREE COMMUNITIES IN SAGBAMA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Required epidemiological data on the prevalence of Intestinal Parasitic Infections (IPIs) and identification of associated risk factors in different regions is a prerequisite to developing appropriate control management. This study was aimed at determining the prevalence of intestinal parasites among primary school children age in public primary schools in three communities (Adagbabiri, Sagbama and Tungbo) in Sagbama Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Pupils in each particular class in a school were randomly selected. 335 stool samples were analyzed for intestinal parasites ova/larvae using the direct method and formol ether concentration technique. 109(32.5%) tested positive for IPIs with more males (37.1%) children than females (28.8%) children were infected. Seven species of parasites were identified; *Entamoeba histolytica* 28(8.4%), *Ascaris lumbricoides* 19(5.7%), *Strongyloides stercoralis* 16(4.8%), *Trichuristrichiura* 14(4.2%), Hookworm 13(3.9%) *Schistosomamansonii* 10(3.0%) and *entamoeba coli* 9(2.7%) in this order. Multiple infections were also encountered recording 8(2.4%). Age bracket 5-7years had the highest prevalence of 66(61.1%). There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$). Intestinal parasite infection is still a public health problem among school children in Sagbama Local Government Area. Therefore the need for improvement of sanitation, health education, provision of potable drinking water and mass deworming exercises through Community Based Intervention (CBT) is essential.